

expected i.r. bands for ν_{N-H} (3200 cm^{-1}) ν_{C-C} (phenyl ring) (1600 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{-N=N-N-}$ (sym. triazene; ($\sim 1560 - 1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $\nu_{N\rightarrow O}$ ($\sim 1300 - 1220\text{ cm}^{-1}$) have all been located in the i.r. spectra of the triazene-1-oxide ligands⁵. $\nu_{N\rightarrow O}$ band is found to be considerably lowered ($\sim 60\text{ cm}^{-1}$) due to N-O-M bond formation⁶⁻⁸. ν_{N-H} band of the ligand completely disappears in the complexes MT_2 , MT_3 and MT_4 (dipy/*o*-phen) showing coordination of the metal ion through N-atom. ν_{C-C} (phenyl ring) remains almost unchanged ($\sim 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$). $\nu_{-N=N-N-}$ is lowered by $\sim 26\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to change in the environment of the symmetric triazene. The $\nu_{N\rightarrow O}$ (1300 cm^{-1}) is lowered to ($\sim 1240\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Both in the homochelates and the mixed chelates the very sharp new band around ($\sim 1240\text{ cm}^{-1}$) also covers a few weak bands as well as ν_{C-C} (phenyl in plane). Characteristic bands of coordinated dipy/*o*-phen as in $[Cu(dipy)Cl_2]$ and $[Cu(o\text{-phen})Cl_2]$ ⁹; $[Ni(OH_2)Cl(dipy)_2]Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$ ¹⁰ around $\sim 730\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\sim 1170\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1470\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed in the spectra of $[CoT_2(dipy/o\text{-phen})]$ complexes. The important i.r. bands have been presented in Table 2.

Experimental

The chelates were prepared by following standard procedures^{4,11,12}. Their characterisation data were satisfactory. Room temperature magnetic moments were measured in Gouy balance using $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as a calibrant. The electronic spectra were run at SIC, Madras and i.r. spectra at C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of bis(ethylmalonato) Co(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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BETA-diketones and beta-keto esters have drawn considerable attention as oxygen donorchelating ligands¹⁻⁶. We have been trying^{7,8} to prepare complexes with nitrogen donors of these metal chelates. We thought it would be worthwhile to extend our investigation to the synthesis of a number of mixed ligand complexes of Co(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions with malonic ester and nitrogen donor aliphatic and heterocyclic amines.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The metal chelates were prepared as reported earlier⁷. Mixed ligand complexes were prepared by refluxing an ethanolic suspension of metal chelates and amines in 1:2 ratio for about two hours over water bath. On keeping the resulting solution overnight, crystalline compounds separated out which were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution. Electronic spectra were recorded in M/100 chloroform solution of the complexes. All the relevant analytical and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

Result and Discussion

All the twelve complexes reported in the present communication have the composition $[ML_2B_2]^0$, where M=Co(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II); L is malonic ester and B is either a heterocyclic or aliphatic amine. Cobalt complexes are brown, copper complexes are green and zinc complexes are white in colour and these complexes have fairly low melting points. Acetone solution of the complexes are found to be non-electrolytes as the ΔM values range between 8 to 12 mhos cm^2 . The μ_{eff} values for Co(II) and Cu(II) complexes are around 5.1 and 1.8 B. M. respectively. In I. R. spectra of the mixed ligand complexes the two bands $\nu(C=O)$ at 1600 cm^{-1} and $\nu(C-O)$ at 1290 cm^{-1} are again shifted to higher frequency regions appearing around 1620 and 1310 cm^{-1} respectively indicating bonding of the σ -bonded amines to the metal ions. Moreover, most of the bands due to nitrogen bases, have been modified in the complexes which indirectly supports the bonding of the nitrogen donor ligands to metal ions. Further, the direct evidence of bonding of oxygen and nitrogen

TABLE 1 - MELTING POINT, ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	M.P. (°C)	% Metal		% Nitrogen		Δ mhos cm ²	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
		Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.						
[CoL ₂ (α -pic) ₂]	178	13.55	14.05	6.35	6.69	9.00	5.1	1620	1310	510	350
[CoL ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]	191	13.51	14.05	6.62	6.69	8.50	4.9	1620	1315	510	250
[CoL ₂ Q ₂]	186	12.02	12.27	5.63	5.70	12.00	5.0	1610	1310	510	340
[CoL ₂ (DMA) ₂]	167	17.97	18.23	8.26	8.62	8.0	5.1	1610	1305	505	345
[CuL ₂ (α -pic) ₂]	212	13.63	15.04	6.17	6.60	10.00	1.8	1615	1310	515	340
[CuL ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]	201	13.58	15.04	6.52	6.60	9.5	1.7	1620	1310	510	350
[CuL ₂ Q ₂]	179	12.71	12.86	5.48	5.64	8.0	1.75	1625	1320	510	350
[CuL ₂ (DEA) ₂]	226*	16.12	16.02	7.01	7.29	12.0	1.8	1610	1310	515	345
[ZnL ₂ (α -pic) ₂]	249*	15.55	15.37	6.29	6.58	8.5	—	1620	1315	515	340
[ZnL ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]	259*	14.86	15.37	6.50	6.58	9.0	—	1615	1310	505	350
[ZnL ₂ Q ₂]	235	13.37	13.14	5.56	5.62	10.0	—	1625	1305	510	340
[ZnL ₂ (DEA) ₂]	286*	17.12	19.96	7.08	7.26	10.5	—	1620	1320	510	345

* decomposition

 α -pic = α -picoline, γ -pic = γ -picoline, Q = quinoline, DMA = dimethylamine, DEA = diethylamine

atoms have been provided by the occurrence of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ around 510 cm⁻¹ and 350 cm⁻¹ respectively.

In the visible electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complexes two absorption bands appear ~18.0(30) and ~8.5(20) k.K. region attributable¹⁰ to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(P) and ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(F) transition respectively. Position of absorption bands, molar absorptivity values and magnetic moment suggest a high spin octahedral configuration for the Co(II) complexes. Copper(II) complexes show one broad absorption band ~15.0(40) k.K. region indicating probably a distorted octahedral configuration, but μ_{eff} values found for Cu(II) complexes are low for Oh symmetry. Although, three transitions are expected for such complexes due to Jahn Teller distortion, often these transitions are observed in the form of a broad envelope, as these are very close in energy. Zinc(II) complexes are presumably octahedral on the basis of analysis, conductance and I. R. spectral data.

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Studies on Complex Compounds of Nickel(II), Palladium(II) and Copper(II) with Benzaldehyde Semicarbazone

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THE present paper reports three complexes, namely, *bis*-benzaldehyde semicarbazone Ni(II), *bis*-benzaldehyde semicarbazone Pd(II) and *bis*-benzaldehyde semicarbazone Cu(II) of the formulae, M(C₆H₅ON₃)₂ where M = Ni(II), Pd(II) and Cu(II).